

STUDIES ON THE ACTIVE PRINCIPLES OF *SKIMMIA LAUREOLA*, HOOK

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An alkaloid, skimmianine ($C_{14}H_{18}O_4N$, m. p. 176-77°), three coumarins, viz. umbelliferone ($C_9H_8O_5$, m. p. 232°), bergapten ($C_{12}H_{10}O_4$, m. p. 188-90°) and isopimpinellin ($C_{13}H_{10}O_5$, m. p. 150°), and a neutral compound, laureoline ($C_{24}H_{32}O_8$, m. p. 258-60°) have been isolated from the leaves and bark of *Skimmia laureola*, Hook.

Skimmia laureola, Hook, a common fodder plant of India, has been the subject of investigations by several workers (Roure-Bertrand, *Fils Bull.*, 1920, 34, 2; *Schimmel. Ber.*, 1926, 46, 3; Simonsen, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1921, 40, 126T; *Schimmel I. C. Constanten*, 1913, 72, 5; Schimmel & Co. Rept. 1932, 5-73; Wienhaus and Rajdhan, *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1936, 147, 113; Chopra, Chatterjee, Dey and Ghosh, *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1938, 26, 481) for the past few years. The presence of an alkaloid, skimmianine, $C_{14}H_{18}O_4N$ (l. m. p. 176-77°), a furocoumarin bergapten, $C_{12}H_{10}O_4$ (ll, m. p. 188-90°), a neutral substance, skimmiol (m. p. 279-81°) and essential oils have been reported to be present in the leaves of this plant.

During the isolation of skimmianine (I) from the leaves of this plant for preparing its authentic sample, it has been observed by the present authors that the leaves of *Skimmia laureola* contain three more active ingredients which have not been recorded so far, by the previous workers. One of these constituents is isopimpinellin ($C_{13}H_{10}O_5$, m. p. 150°), a dimethoxyfurocoumarin; the second one is umbelliferone, a 7-hydroxycoumarin ($C_9H_8O_5$, m. p. 232°, yield, 0.1%) and the third compound is laureoline, a neutral substance ($C_{24}H_{32}O_8$, m. p. 258-60°, yield 0.02%) which appears to be hitherto unknown. The bark of this plant has also been investigated and five crystalline constituents, viz., the alkaloid skimmianine, three coumarins and the same neutral compound, laureoline, have been isolated, the properties and constitution of which are described herein.

Skimmianine, $C_{14}H_{18}ON(QCH_3)_3$ (yield 0.05%), the optically inactive, weak and tertiary base (which distils unchanged in vacuum at 150°/0.1 mm.) was obtained on basification of the acid digest of the ethereal extract of the powdered bark of *Skimmia laureola*.

The sodium carbonate digest of the residual solution precipitated umbelliferone (yield 0.1%) on acidification.

The neutral ether extract of the bark deposited laureoline. It does not give any coloration with ferric chloride. It is insoluble in alkali and does not produce any characteristic coloration with steroidal reagents. Laureoline dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a yellow colour. It is free from methoxy and methylene-dioxy groups. Further work on the elucidation on the structure of laureoline is in progress which will be reported later.

A mixture of bergapten (yield 0.3%) and isopimpinellin (yield 0.005%) was obtained from the saponifiable portion of the neutral extract.

EXPERIMENTAL

Air-dried powdered leaves of *Skimmia laureola* (800.0 g.) were soxhletted with ether (2 litres) for 48 hours. The greenish brown ethereal extract was shaken with 0.1% hydrochloric acid (300 c. c. in three instalments) when skimmianine passed into the acid layer. The brown, non-basic ether solution (P) was kept aside, and the brown acid extract (Q) was worked up for the isolation of skimmianine.

Isolation of Skimmianine from (Q).—The acid aqueous solution (Q; *vide supra*) was cooled in ice water and basified with sodium bicarbonate. The base separating was taken up in chloroform (100 c. c.), washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and distilled. The residue (0.4 g.), left on removal of the solvent, crystallised from ethyl acetate in colorless prisms, m. p. 176-77°. On repeated crystallisations from ethanol, acetone and ethyl acetate, the m. p. remained unchanged. (Found: C, 65.06; H, 4.86; N, 5.51; OMe, 36.02. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N$: C, 64.86; H, 5.02; N, 5.41; OMe, 35.96 per cent).

The *picrate* was prepared by adding an ethereal solution of picric acid to an ethereal solution of skimmianine. The yellow precipitate crystallised from alcohol in yellow plates, m. p. 193-94° (decomp.). [Found: N, 11.29. Calc. for $C_{14}H_{13}O_4N, C_6H_2OH(NO_2)_3$: N, 11.48 per cent].

The *chloroplatinate* was prepared by adding an aqueous solution of platinum chloride (5%) to a faintly hydrochloric acid solution of skimmianine. Upon crystallisation from water containing a little hydrochloric acid glistening orange coloured plates were obtained, which did not melt but charred at 200°. [Found: Pt, 20.82, 20.68. Calc. for $(C_{14}H_{13}O_4N)_2, H_2PtCl_6$: Pt, 21.01 per cent].

Isolation of Umbelliferone from the fraction (P).—The non-basic, brown ether solution (P) was digested with an aqueous solution of sodium carbonate (2N, 100 c. c.) when umbelliferone was dissolved out of the ether layer into the carbonate solution (Q) which exhibited a deep violet fluorescence. The neutral ether portion left was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, concentrated to a small bulk (P') and kept in the frigidaire. The carbonate solution (Q; *vide supra*) was acidified with hydrochloric acid when umbelliferone separated. It was taken up with ether and the ethereal solution was washed with water, dried and freed from the solvent. The residue crystallised from ethyl acetate in glistening needles, m. p. 232° and showed no depression in m. p. when mixed with synthetic umbelliferone. (Found: C, 66.30; H, 3.88. Calc. for $C_9H_6O_3$: C, 66.67; H, 3.70 per cent).

Methylation of umbelliferone was effected by refluxing an acetone solution (dried over potassium carbonate) of it with freshly distilled methyl iodide in presence of potassium carbonate for 6 hours. It crystallised from methanol in colorless needles,

m. p. 119° and showed no change in m. p. when admixed with synthetic methylumbelliferone. [Found : OMe, 17.63. Calc. for $C_9H_5O_2(OCH_3)$: OMe, 17.62 per cent].

Isolation of Laureoline from the fraction (P').—The neutral ethereal extract (P') on keeping in the frigidaire deposited laureoline after four weeks. Laureoline was collected and separated from the adhering gum by washing with ether. It crystallised from ethanol and acetone in rhombic plates, m. p. 258-60°. [Found : C, 63.80 ; H, 7.21 ; M. W. (by Rast's method), 440, 436. Calc. for $C_{24}H_{32}O_8$: C, 64.28 ; H, 7.14 per cent. M. W., 448].

The neutral extract left after the separation of laureoline was freed from the solvent and the oil obtained was worked up by the method of Späth and Socias (*Ber.*, 1934, 67, 59) for the isolation of bergapten and isopimpinellin. The oil was cooled to about 15° and to it was added 200 c. c. of 20% methyl alcoholic potassium hydroxide solution with constant stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for 45 minutes, then poured into one litre of ice water and the aqueous solution was extracted with ether to remove non-saponifiable portions. The reddish brown aqueous alkaline solution was acidified with hydrochloric acid (Congo red) and allowed to stand overnight. Next morning the greater portion of methyl alcohol was removed under reduced pressure, then cooled and thrice extracted with ether (300 c. c.). The ether digest was washed with an aqueous solution of potassium carbonate (100 c. c., 25%), then with water and finally dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The residue left on removal of the solvent solidified on keeping in a frigidaire for a week. The solid (R) was washed with light petrol (b. p. 40°-60°) when glistening yellow needles mixed up with shining, colorless needles were obtained.

Isolation of Bergapten and isoPimpinellin from the fraction (R).—The fraction (R ; *vide supra* ; yield, 3.2 g.) was thrice crystallised from methanol when colorless, silky needles of bergapten of m.p. 184-86° separated. These were collected and the mother-liquor (R') was kept for further investigation. Crude bergapten, m.p. 184-86°, (2.0g) distilled at 150-55°/0.1 mm. The colorless distillate quickly solidified and was recrystallised from ethyl acetate and methanol when m. p. could be raised to 188-90°. [Found : C, 67.06 ; H, 4.03 ; OMe, 14.40. Calc. for $C_{11}H_8O_3(OCH_3)$: C, 66.67 ; H, 3.70 ; OMe, 14.35 per cent].

The sample showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with a pure sample of bergapten.

Isolation of isoPimpinellin from R'.—The mother-liquor (R' ; *vide supra*) on removal of the solvent was distilled in high vacuum when two different fractions were obtained. The first fraction (A) (yield 0.04 g.) was collected at 115°-120°/0.1 mm. and the second (B) (yield 0.4g.) at 150°-155°/0.1 mm. The fraction (A) crystallised from ethyl acetate, methanol and 50% ethyl alcohol in yellow glistening needles, m.p. 150°. It showed no change in m.p. when mixed with an authentic sample of isopimpinellin. [Found : C, 62.92 ; H, 3.89 ; OMe, 24.86. Calc. $C_{11}H_8O_3(OCH_3)_2$: C, 63.41 ; H, 4.06 ; OMe, 25.2 per cent].

The second fraction of the distillate was crystallised from alcohol when silky needles of bergapten, m.p. 188-190° separated. Its m.p. remained unchanged when mixed with an authentic sample of bergapten.

The same experimental procedure (described above) has been followed for the isolation and identification of active principles of the bark of *S. laureola*.

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